

Capability and Acceptance of Filipino to Adopt Advanced Nursing Practice

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ABSTRACT

Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP) is increasingly recognized as a vital strategy to strengthen healthcare systems and improve patient outcomes. In an attempt to bridge the gap in healthcare, the Philippine Legislature had proposed amendment of the Republic Act 9173 known as the Philippine nursing act of 2002 and is currently awaiting executive approval. With its imminent advent, this study aimed to determine the Filipino nurses' level of capability and their acceptance of its adoption, and also to examine the relationship between these variables. A descriptive-correlational research design was utilized, employing total enumeration sampling with 159 registered nurses in a selected healthcare institution. A survey questionnaire measured the Filipino nurses' capability and its attributes - skills, knowledge, experience, and competencies based on Hamric's framework as well as their degree of acceptance with their awareness, attitude and willingness to adopt Advanced Nursing Practice was used to gather data. Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were used to summarize the data, while a chi-square test of independence, Spearman's rho, were applied to test the relationship between profiles, capability and acceptance. Findings revealed that Filipino nurses demonstrated very high levels of capability and acceptance towards adoption of ANP. Additionally, a statistically significant correlation was identified between capability and acceptance, suggesting that elevated levels of capability correlate with increased acceptability of ANP adoption. The findings indicate that augmenting nurses' competencies via education, training, mentorship, and skill enhancement may facilitate their acceptance and capability in ANP integration. These results give policymakers, nursing educators, and healthcare administrators useful information that will help them get the nursing workforce ready for possible integration of advanced practice nursing in the Philippines.

KEYWORDS: acceptance, capability, Advanced Nursing Practice, Advanced Practice Nursing

INTRODUCTION

Nursing as a profession has consistently adapted to the demands of contemporary healthcare. Advanced Practice Nursing (APN) has substantially transformed the conventional roles of nurses worldwide by broadening their responsibilities to include advanced clinical assessment, autonomous decision-making, prescribing, and leadership within multidisciplinary teams (Pulcini et al., 2019). Countries including the United States, Australia, Canada, the United Kingdom, and others have long had advanced nursing roles. They know that these roles help fill workforce gaps, make health services more accessible, and improve patient outcomes (Woo et al., 2020). These roles may be referred to as Advanced Practice Nursing (APN) and Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP), sometimes used interchangeably, refers to the scope of practice. Although Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP) is becoming increasingly well-known in the Philippines, especially among medical professionals, it still lacks official legal recognition and public awareness. Despite being acknowledged as a way to address healthcare shortages and advance Universal Health Care (UHC), its implementation is primarily institution-based due to the lack of a legislative framework (Marsh et al., 2026).

There are also gaps in education, as there are no standardized, specialized training pathways officially recognized as Advanced Practice Nursing (Vitug, 2025). Environmental barriers, such as the lack of regulatory frameworks, and financing, educational pathways, limit the institutionalization of APNs (Tamayo, 2025). In addition, social, and professional impediments are also identified (Vitug, 2025).

With a population of about 109 million, there are about 88.5 thousand nurses and 28.8 thousand doctors (Statista, 2021). Nurses makes up a large portion of the healthcare workforce in the country and Filipino nurses are prepared for significant transformations in the nursing practice and it is time for Filipino nurses to advance to an expert level of professional practice (Domocmat, 2019).

The Philippine Nursing Act, Republic Act 9173 (2002), is the primary regulation that governs nursing profession in the Philippines. In order to correspond to modern standards, the law established requirements for education, postgraduate studies, and nursing qualifications. The law simply specifies that nursing practice will involve training in nursing, health, and human resource development as well as conducting research to promote advanced nursing practice (Official Gazette, 2002). In 2015, the Comprehensive Nursing Act of 2015, a bill amending Republic Act 9173, was again presented to the Senate, prepared by the Senate Committees, spearheaded by Ralph Recto, Antonio Trillanes, and Ferdinand "Bongbong" Marcos, among many others. Section 46 of the said bill, entitled Advanced Practice Nursing program, mandates the formulation and development of the Advanced Practice Nursing Program to upgrade the skills and competence of nurses nationwide (Senate Bill 2720, 2015). However, the bill was vetoed by former President Benigno Aquino III due to conflicts with existing government salary structures and could undermine the government's strict tax collection efforts (Update Philippines, 2016). A more recent amendment was made in 2022, with it passing the third reading and awaiting the executive approval from the President (Senate Bill 1447, 2022).

Are the Filipino nurses prepared and capable to adopt it? If the integration is forthcoming, it is imperative to assess Filipino nurses' acceptance and capability towards adopting ANP. Capability is a blend of competencies, knowledge, skills, and experience that allows the nurses to perform efficiently in advanced roles (Whitfield et al, 2022). Acceptance, on the other hand, is the willingness, awareness, and attitude towards the added role (Sekhon et al., 2017; Mrazek et al., 2024; Klussman, 2022). Comprehending these two constructs clarifies the nursing profession's preparedness to embrace Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP), providing evidence to inform curriculum development, workforce training, and policymaking specific to the Philippine context.

This study is anchored in Benner's Novice to Expert Theory (Benner, 1984), which explains how nurses develop capability for Advanced Practice Nursing (APN) through progressive stages of clinical experience and skill acquisition. Capability refers to nurses' knowledge, skills, experience, and competencies, evolving from rule-dependent practice at the novice level to intuitive and flexible decision-making at the expert level. As nurses advance across these stages, their ability to perform complex roles increases, demonstrating that expertise develops through experiential learning.

Acceptance of APN is likewise influenced by nurses' level of expertise. More experienced nurses are more likely to recognize the value of expanded roles and responsibilities. Acceptance is measured through awareness, attitude, and willingness to adopt APN. These attributes are supported by Sekhon et al. (2017), who identify attitude and willingness as key components of acceptability, and by Klussmann et al. (2022), who emphasize awareness as a foundational precursor to acceptance. Furthermore, these dimensions align with Diffusion of Innovations (Rogers, 2003), which describes adoption as a process moving from awareness (knowledge), to attitude formation (persuasion), and finally to decision (willingness to adopt) (Mohammadi et al., 2018).

In this framework, capability serves as the predictor variable, measured through self-perceived knowledge, skills, experience, and competencies, while acceptance is the outcome variable, measured by awareness, attitude, and willingness to adopt ANP. Demographic characteristics such as age, years of experience, and educational attainment are treated as control variables. Overall, capability represents nurses' functional readiness, whereas acceptance reflects their psychological readiness—two distinct but complementary constructs essential for the adoption of advanced nursing practice.

Capability to Adopt ANP

Capability in adopting Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP) extends beyond competencies. It is better understood as the integration of knowledge, skills, experience, judgment, and resources to manage complex and unfamiliar clinical situations (Whitfield et al., 2024). While studies on ANP capability remain limited, existing Philippine research highlights that nurses demonstrate strengths in leadership, communication, and community practice

but require further development in public health science and financial management (Cariaso et al., 2024). Exposure to advanced practice roles through inter-professional collaboration has been shown to enhance nurses' understanding, particularly in primary care, chronic disease management, and culturally competent care, ultimately improving healthcare accessibility and service delivery (Marsh et al., 2026). Despite the absence of a formal ANP policy, Filipino nurses already perform functions aligned with advanced practice frameworks, supported by national competency standards and continuous professional development programs (Abaquin, 2016; Cruz, 2024; PRC, 2012). Core competencies such as leadership, collaboration, research, and ethical decision-making—outlined in Hamric's model—are essential but highly dependent on contextual and environmental factors (Cooke et al., 2008; Spruce, 2005). Furthermore, clinical experience and structured education, reinforced by mentorship, are critical in developing advanced clinical competence, professional identity, and readiness for expanded nursing roles (Leonardsen, 2023; Swenson, 2025).

Acceptance of Adopting ANP

Acceptance of Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP) is generally characterized by positive attitudes among nurses; however, this does not consistently translate into strong intention or readiness to pursue the role, indicating a gap between acceptance and actual uptake (Woo et al., 2020). Successful integration of ANP requires recognition and support from healthcare professionals and institutions, as lack of understanding may lead to role ambiguity, resistance, and limited autonomy (Schober, 2016).

Evidence from Pakistan shows generally high awareness and positive attitudes toward ANPs among healthcare professionals, particularly regarding their role in emergency care, although clearer role definitions and stronger institutional support are still needed for full integration (Pervez, 2025). Similarly, acceptance is influenced by limited educational pathways and early-stage development of ANP programs, despite recognition of their potential to improve healthcare outcomes (Moafa et al., 2025).

In the Philippines, acceptance remains constrained by the absence of formal legal recognition, regulatory frameworks, and financing mechanisms. Although ANP is viewed as a potential strategy to address workforce gaps and support Universal Health Care, its implementation is still largely institution-based due to systemic, professional, and policy-related barriers (Marsh et al., 2026; Tamayo, 2025; Vitug, 2025).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to determine the level of capability and acceptance of adoption of Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP) among Filipino nurses. Specifically, it seeks to describe the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest level of attainment, years of clinical experience, and area of clinical practice. It also aims to assess the level of capability in adopting ANP in terms of knowledge, skills, experience and APN core competencies based on Hamric's framework, as well as determine the level of acceptance toward the adoption of ANP through awareness, willingness and attitude. Furthermore, the study intends to examine whether there is a significant relationship between capability and acceptance of adopting ANP. Finally, the findings of the study are expected to provide insights for policy making bodies and for the development of ANP education and practice and awareness programs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive–correlational research design. Quantitative methods were used to systematically analyze numerical data through statistical techniques (Sheard, 2019). The descriptive component aimed to determine the levels of capability and acceptance of Filipino nurses toward advanced nursing practice (ANP), while the correlational component examined the relationship between these variables and the influence of selected demographic factors.

Participants and Setting

The target population consisted of registered nurses employed in a private hospital in Bacolod City, Philippines. Respondent descriptors were: (1) Filipino registered nurses, (2) with at least one year of clinical experience, (3) currently employed in a healthcare institution, and (4) assigned to clinical areas such as medical–surgical wards, obstetrics and gynecology, pediatrics, emergency room, hemodialysis, intensive care, outpatient services, and operating room. Nurses in purely administrative or academic roles were excluded.

Nurses with less than one year of experience were also excluded, consistent with Benner’s (1982) framework, which suggests that early-stage practitioners have limited prioritization and decision-making capacity.

Sampling Technique

A non-probability sampling approach using total enumeration was applied. A list of eligible nurses was obtained from the hospital’s human resources office, and all qualified individuals were invited to participate. The 159 eligible nurses consented and completed the survey. This approach allowed comprehensive coverage of the accessible population, minimizing selection bias and enhancing contextual representativeness. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was secured prior to data collection.

Research Instrument

Data were collected through a structured, researcher-developed questionnaire consisting of three parts:

1. Demographic Profile – age, sex, years of clinical experience, and area of practice.
2. Capability Scale – 27 items measuring knowledge, skills, experience, and advanced practice nursing competencies, based on the International Council of Nurses (ICN) guidelines and Hamric’s framework (Schober, 2016; 2020). Responses were rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Very Poor to 5 = Excellent).
3. Acceptance Scale – 15 items assessing awareness, attitude, and willingness, constructed in reference to ICN guidelines and related literature (Mrazek et al., 2024; Sekhon, 2017; Schober, 2016;2020), using a 5-point scale (1 = Not at all to 5 = Completely).

Weighted mean scores were computed and interpreted using equal-interval classification of Likert scales (Boone & Boone, 2012).

Validity and Reliability

Content validity was established through expert evaluation by five nursing professionals involved in nursing research. Using Lawshe’s Content Validity Ratio (CVR), the instrument achieved an overall Content Validity Index (CVI) of 0.95, indicating excellent validity. Three items with sub-threshold CVR values were revised for clarity and construct alignment rather than removed.

Face validity was assessed using the Good and Scates method, yielding a mean score of 4.82, interpreted as very good, indicating that the instrument was clear and appropriate for measuring the constructs.

Reliability testing was conducted through a pilot study involving 29 respondents. Cronbach’s alpha coefficient was 0.974, indicating excellent internal consistency and high interrelatedness among items.

Data Collection Procedure

Ethical approval was obtained from both the university and hospital ethics committees prior to data collection. Questionnaires were distributed in both paper-based and online formats (via Google Forms) to accommodate respondent preferences.

Data collection spanned three weeks. Paper questionnaires were distributed across hospital units, while follow-ups were conducted through in-person visits and online messaging to improve response rates, particularly among shift-based staff. Completed responses were compiled into a database for analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using JAMOVI version 2.7.14. Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were used to summarize respondent characteristics and key variables. Respondents were categorized as follows: Age: younger (22–30) and older (31–60). Sex : male and female; Highest educational attainment (Bachelor, Master’s Degree, Doctorate Degree) Clinical experience: grouped according to Benner’s stages (advanced beginner to expert) .Chi-square tests of independence were used to examine relationships between demographic variables and categorized levels of capability and acceptance. The chi-square square test of independence and Spearman’s rho was employed to determine the association between the profiles, capability and acceptance. Non-parametric tests were used due to non-normal data distribution, as indicated by the Shapiro–Wilk test.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles were strictly observed throughout the study. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained prior to survey completion. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by excluding identifying information and reporting the institution as a “private hospital.” Data were securely stored in a restricted-access digital repository. Hard copies were safeguarded and scheduled for disposal after two years, alongside deletion of digital files.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the study on the capability and acceptance of Filipino nurses to adopt Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP) presents the data collected from respondents systematically and provides a thorough analysis and interpretation aligned with the study's goals and objectives.

The findings are organized according to the constructs of this study and the control variables identified. It includes presenting the level of capability of Filipino nurses based on respondents' knowledge, experience, APN Competencies, and skills. The level of acceptance among the respondents is also discussed, with an exploration of their awareness, willingness, and attitudes. Both constructs are analyzed in terms of their age, sex, years of clinical practice, and years in clinical areas. Statistical analyses were used to determine significant relationships and patterns among variables.

Furthermore, this chapter discusses the implications of the findings in the context of current literature. The results are intended to provide insights into Filipino nurses' capabilities, acceptance of the adoption of ANP, and contributions to the development of advanced nursing practice in the country. The findings are intended to provide light on how prepared Filipino nurses are to take on more responsibilities.

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Demographic Data

Table 1. The profile of the respondents

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percent
Age		
Younger (31 years old and below)	85	53.5
Older (Above 31 years old)	74	46.5
Sex		
Male	48	30.2
Female	111	69.8
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor’s Degree	149	93.7
Master’s Degree	9	5.7
Doctorate Degree	1	0.6
Years of Clinical Experience		
Advance Beginner	68	42.8
Competent	25	15.7
Proficient	34	21.4

Expert	32	20.1
Total	159	100.0

Table 1 reflects the respondents' demographic and professional profiles, providing a background for understanding their capability and acceptance of advanced nursing practice.

In terms of age, 74 (46.5%) of the respondents are older than 31, while 85 (53.5%) are younger nurses. When evaluating preparedness for ANP adoption across various career stages, this distribution is relatively balanced, indicating representation from both early-career and more seasoned age groups.

Regarding sex, there are more female respondents (111, 69.8%) than male respondents (48, 30.2%) in the sample. It suggests that the results may mostly reflect the viewpoints of female nurses and reflect the overall gender distribution in the nursing profession in the Philippines.

Regarding educational attainment, the majority of respondents (149, or 93.7%) have a Bachelor's degree. At the same time, only a small percentage have pursued graduate studies: 1 (0.6%) holds a doctorate and 9 (5.7%) hold a Master's. It indicates that respondents had limited advanced academic preparation, which could affect their capability and acceptance to assume advanced nursing responsibilities that often require higher education.

In the years of clinical experience, Advanced Beginners (68 or 42.8%) make up the largest group, followed by Proficient nurses (34 or 21.4%), Experts (32 or 20.1%), and Competent nurses (25 or 15.7%). This distribution shows a notable number of highly experienced nurses, even though a sizable fraction of respondents is still in the early stages of skill development.

According to the profile, the majority of responses are from young, female individuals with Bachelor's degrees and varying levels of clinical experience, most of which are in the advanced beginners, and competent stages. These traits are crucial in determining their capability and acceptance to adopt ANP, as factors such as professional development, education, and experience can significantly impact their preparedness to assume advanced nursing roles.

It is consistent with the study by Macha et al. (2024), which found that Filipino nurses are predominantly female and that the majority are in the 25-30 age group; this age group was mostly at the advanced beginner to competent level. 90 percent have a Bachelor's degree, and a smaller portion take up post-graduate studies (Macha et al., 2024; Denney,2022)

The distribution of respondents by area of practice is presented in Table 2 and provides more detail on the demographic profile in Table 1.

Table 2. Profile of the respondents in terms of area and years of practice

Area of Expertise	Frequency	Percent
<i>Medical Surgical Unit</i>	75	58.1
Advanced Beginner	39	52.0
Competent	12	16.0
Proficient	21	28.0
Expert	3	4.0
<i>Obstetrics and Gynecology Unit</i>	27	16.9
Advanced Beginner	11	40.7
Competent	9	33.3
Proficient	4	14.8
Expert	3	11.1
<i>Pediatric Unit</i>	22	13.8
Advanced Beginner	14	63.6
Competent	5	22.7
Proficient	2	9.1
Expert	1	4.5

ER	35	13.2
Advanced Beginner	18	52.4
Competent	11	31.4
Proficient	4	11.4
Expert	2	5.7
Hemodialysis/Renal Care Unit	37	23.3
Advanced Beginner	17	45.9
Competent	13	35.1
Proficient	7	18.9
Expert	0	0
Intensive and Critical Care Unit	18	11.3
Advanced Beginner	6	33.3
Competent	7	38.9
Proficient	2	11.1
Expert	3	16.7
Outpatient	7	4.4
Advanced Beginner	4	57.1
Competent	3	42.9
Proficient	0	0
Expert	0	0
OR	21	13.2
Advanced Beginner	9	42.9
Competent	5	23.8
Proficient	5	23.8
Expert	2	9.5

The majority of the respondents (75, or 58.1%) have clinical exposure in the Medical-Surgical Unit. Advanced beginners make up the majority of this category (52.0%), followed by proficient (28.0%), competent (16.0%), and experts (4.0%). This trend supports the previous conclusion that, despite being in high-exposure areas, a significant section of the respondents is still in the early stages of developing clinical skills.

The majority of units show a similar pattern. Advanced beginners make up the largest grouping with clinical exposure in the Pediatric Unit (63.6%), ER (52.4%), Outpatient (57.1%), and Emergency Services Unit (50.0%). It indicates that a large number of nurses, irrespective of specialization, are still acquiring basic competencies. The prevalence of early-stage practitioners suggests possible shortcomings in their immediate preparedness for ANP positions, which often require advanced clinical judgment and independence.

Some units, however, have comparatively higher levels of experience. Although none of the respondents fell into the expert category, the distribution of advanced beginners (45.9%) and competent nurses (35.1%) in the Hemodialysis/Renal Care Unit is more balanced. In contrast, the Intensive and Critical Care Unit (ICCU) has a more advanced skill mix, with a significant percentage of competent (38.9%) and expert nurses (16.7%). Given the high-acuity nature of critical care, which necessitates better clinical proficiency, this is to be expected.

Additionally, the Obstetrics and Gynecology Unit shows a fairly uniform distribution of clinical experience levels, with competent nurses (33.3%), advanced beginners (40.7%), and a small percentage of experts (11.1%). On the other hand, there is no representation of the Outpatient Department in the proficient and expert levels, indicating a lack of exposure to intricate clinical decision-making.

Overall, the statistics show that respondents are spread across a variety of clinical specialties. Expert practitioners are only more prevalent in a few specialized fields, with each field having only 0-3 nurses.

In a study by Macha et al.,(2024) most nurses with 1-3 years of experience work in general wards, suggesting that the majority are advanced beginners practicing in medical-surgical units. The study also wants to point out that those in the expert level (10 years and above years of experience) is only 20% of the population. The study

would like to stress that the expert workforce may have opted to work and migrate abroad for a better future. (Lorenzo, 2007; Elmaco, 2022)

Level of Capability of Filipino Nurses to Adopt ANP

Table 3.a. The level of capability of the respondents to adopt advance nursing practice (knowledge and skills)

Profile Variables	Knowledge			Skills		
	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int
Age						
Younger	4.19	0.55	G	4.13	0.65	G
Older	4.30	0.57	EX	4.28	0.63	EX
Sex						
Male	4.27	0.61	EX	4.15	0.65	G
Female	4.23	0.53	EX	4.23	0.64	EX
Educational Attainment						
Bachelor's Degree	4.21	0.55	EX	4.17	0.64	G
Master's Degree	4.67	0.50	EX	4.67	0.50	EX
Doctorate Degree	5.00		EX	5.00		EX
Years of Clinical Experience						
Advance Beginner	4.13	0.60	G	4.10	0.69	G
Competent	4.32	0.48	EX	4.28	0.61	EX
Proficient	4.21	0.48	EX	4.21	0.59	EX
Expert	4.44	0.56	EX	4.34	0.60	EX
Taken Collectively	4.24	0.56	EX	4.20	0.64	EX

Category: Very Poor (VP) (1.0-1.80), Poor (P) (1.81-2.60), Fair (F)(2.61-3.40), Good (G) (3.41-4.20), Excellent (EX) (4.21-5.00)

Table 3.b. The level of capability of the respondents to adopt advance nursing practice (experience and competencies)

Profile Variables	Experience			APN Competencies		
	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int
Age						
Younger	4.38	0.58	EX	4.27	0.61	EX
Older	4.46	0.60	EX	4.42	0.64	EX
Sex						
Male	4.42	0.61	EX	4.42	0.61	EX
Female	4.41	0.58	EX	4.31	0.63	EX
Educational Attainment						
Bachelor's Degree	4.39	0.59	EX	4.32	0.63	EX
Master's Degree	4.78	0.44	EX	4.67	0.50	EX
Doctorate Degree	5.00		EX	5.00		EX
Years of Clinical Experience						
Advance Beginner	4.32	0.61	EX	4.25	0.70	EX
Competent	4.44	0.51	EX	4.28	0.46	EX
Proficient	4.47	0.62	EX	4.35	0.60	EX
Expert	4.53	0.57	EX	4.56	0.56	EX
Taken Collectively	4.42	0.59	EX	4.34	0.63	EX

Category: Very Poor (VP)(1.0-1.80), Poor (P)(1.81-2.60), Fair (F)(2.61-3.40), Good (G)(3.41-4.20), Excellent (EX) (4.21-5.00)

Table 3.a presents the level of capability of the respondents to adopt Advanced Nursing (ANP) in terms of knowledge, skills, experience, and APN competencies when categorized based on profile variables.

The collective mean ratings for knowledge (M = 4.24), skills (M = 4.20), experience (M = 4.42), and competencies (M = 4.34), all of which are evaluated as having excellent capability, indicate that respondents generally demonstrated a high level of capability. It suggests that although they are not yet at the "excellent" level, Filipino nurses generally believe they are capable of assuming advanced nursing roles.

Younger nurses had mean scores in the Good level of capability (Knowledge M = 4.19, Skills M = 4.13), with older nurses exhibiting somewhat higher scores in knowledge, skills, experience, and competencies. It implies that perceived capability is influenced by age, which may be correlated with maturity and exposure.

When grouped by age, both younger and older nurses had mean scores in the Good Capability range, with older nurses exhibiting somewhat higher scores in knowledge, skills, experience, and competencies. It implies that perceived capability is influenced by age, which may be correlated with maturity and exposure.

Regarding sex, female respondents reported Excellent Capability across all domains. Male respondents, on the other hand, also had Excellent results except for the skills, with M = 4.15, Good capability. It suggests that sex has little bearing on the ability to adopt APN.

For educational attainment, a definite upward trend is observed. Bachelor's degree holders showed a Good level of capability for knowledge and skills and Excellent level for Experience, APN Competencies, while Master's and Doctoral degree holders showed an Excellent level of capability across all disciplines. This research demonstrates that advanced education significantly improves nurses' preparedness for ANP positions, particularly in developing advanced knowledge, clinical skills, and professional competencies.

When grouped by years of clinical experience, all categories—from competent to Expert—fall within the Excellent capability range. Expert nurses receive the highest marks across all domains, but mean scores gradually increase with experience. It implies that clinical experience deepens and enhances confidence in carrying out advanced responsibilities, even when less experienced nurses feel capable. Experience improves capabilities in nursing, mastering essential skills and improving outcomes (Leonardsen, 2023).

Overall, the results suggest that Filipino nurses have a strong foundation for ANP adoption; however, ongoing investment in clinical skill development and advanced education is necessary to achieve optimal readiness.

Level of Acceptance of the Filipino Nurses to adopt ANP

Table 4. The level of acceptance of the respondents to adopt advance nursing practice

Profile Variables	Attitude			Awareness			Willingness		
	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int
Age									
Younger	4.66	0.50	VH	4.32	0.68	VH	4.45	0.65	VH
Older	4.69	0.50	VH	4.23	0.71	VH	4.35	0.73	VH
Sex									
Male	4.67	0.48	VH	4.35	0.64	VH	4.52	0.58	VH
Female	4.68	0.51	VH	4.24	0.72	VH	4.35	0.72	VH
Educational Attainment									
Bachelor's Degree	4.66	0.50	VH	4.26	0.70	VH	4.38	0.68	VH
Master's Degree	4.89	0.33	VH	4.56	0.53	VH	4.67	0.51	VH
Doctorate Degree	5.00		VH	5.00		VH	5.00		VH
Years of Clinical Experience									
Advance	4.63	0.49	VH	4.32	0.68	VH	4.35	0.69	VH

Beginner												
Competent	4.72	0.46	VH	4.32	0.63	VH	4.52	0.65	VH			
Proficient	4.71	0.58	VH	4.24	0.70	VH	4.38	0.70	VH			
Expert	4.69	0.47	VH	4.19	0.78	H	4.56	0.62	VH			
Taken Collectively	4.67	0.50	VH	4.28	0.69	VH	4.40	0.69	VH			

Category: Very Low (VL)(1.0-1.80), Low (L)(1.81-2.60), Moderate (M)(2.61-3.40), High (H) (3.41-4.20), Very High (VH)(4.21-5.00)

Table 4 presents Filipino nurses' levels of acceptance toward the adoption of Advanced Nursing Practice (AN) in terms of attitude, awareness, and willingness.

Overall, the respondents demonstrated a very high level of acceptance, with a collective mean of 4.45 (Very High level). In particular, awareness (M = 4.28, Very High) and willingness (M = 4.40, Very High), and attitude (M = 4.67) is classified as Very High (VH). It suggests that, even though nurses have positive views and a willingness to support ANP, their awareness may still need strengthening, as indicated by the lowest overall mean score of 4.28.

When grouped by age, with only slight variations in mean scores, both younger and older nurses display Very High levels of attitude. Regardless of experience or maturity, awareness and willingness in both groups remain at the Mostly Acceptable level, indicating that acceptance is generally high across age groups.

Regarding sex, both male and female respondents show Very High attitudes toward APN. Male respondents demonstrate a slightly higher willingness than females (Very High), although both groups maintain a very high level of overall acceptance. It implies that gender does not significantly influence acceptance, consistent with the capability findings in Table 8.

For educational attainment, there is a noticeable upward trend. In contrast, respondents with Master's and Doctorate degrees exhibit Very High levels across all categories. Interestingly, those with a doctorate received perfect mean scores (5.00), signifying the highest level of acceptance. It supports the previous observation (Table 4) that ANP acceptance and capability are greatly increased by better educational preparation.

This result is in accordance with the study by Woo, et al. (2020) where nurses in that study displayed optimism and acceptance towards APN despite its introduction as a new concept.

In connection with Table 2, where respondents demonstrated very high capability, the findings in Table 4 reveal that acceptance is even higher than capability. It implies that, even though some may not feel entirely equipped to take on such responsibilities, Filipino nurses are typically receptive to and supportive of ANP adoption. As demonstrated in awareness and attitude studies in Pakistan that Healthcare administrators and physicians as well as the nurses mostly recognized Advanced Nursing roles as an advancement in nursing and improvement in healthcare due to its perceived contribution to patient care (Pervez, 2025). Likewise, to convert a favourable perception into complete preparedness, the disparity between awareness and attitude underscores the need for improved information dissemination, training initiatives, and policy support among stakeholders.

Relationship between Profile and Capability

Table 5. The significant relationship between the respondent's profile and their level of capability to adopt advanced nursing practice

Profile Variables	Knowledge			Skills			Experience			APN Competencies		
	χ^2	p	Int	χ^2	p	Int	χ^2	p	Int	χ^2	p	Int
Age	1.84	0.40	NS	2.29	0.32	NS	1.50	0.47	NS	3.72	0.16	NS
Sex	1.30	0.52	NS	0.51	0.77	NS	0.33	0.85	NS	1.06	0.59	NS
Educational Attainment	8.67	0.07	NS	7.56	0.11	NS	5.07	0.28	NS	4.11	0.39	NS

Years of Clinical Experience	12.8	0.05	S	5.63	0.47	NS	5.28	0.51	NS	14.1	0.03	S
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Note: S-Significant; NS-Not Significant

Table 5 presents the significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their level of capability to adopt advanced nursing practice (ANP), specifically in terms of experience, skills, and APN competencies. knowledge.

The results show that there is no statistically significant relationship between nurses' ability to adopt advanced nursing practice and most profile characteristics, including age, sex, and educational attainment. P-values greater than 0.05 in every domain (knowledge, skills, experience) support this. It implies that Filipino nurses' capability or readiness to take on advanced nursing jobs is unaffected by these demographic traits.

However, the years of clinical experience and APN competencies have a p-value of 0.03, indicating that nurses with more clinical experience typically possess greater competencies and higher levels of knowledge about advanced nursing practice. Years of clinical experience, on the other hand, did not significantly correlate with the skill and experience domains. It can be supported by the study by Leonardsen (2023) that prior clinical experience contributes to ANP competence.

This research may assume that there is no significant relationship with most of the profile variables, except for years of clinical experience in the capability domain, especially knowledge, and APN competencies.

Relationship between Profile and Acceptance

Table 6. The significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of acceptance to adopt advance nursing practice

Profile Variables	Attitude			Awareness			Willingness		
	χ^2	p	Int	χ^2	p	Int	χ^2	p	Int
Age	0.22	0.90	NS	1.60	0.66	NS	1.75	0.42	NS
Sex	1.13	0.57	NS	1.35	0.72	NS	3.51	0.17	NS
Educational Attainment	2.34	0.67	NS	3.21	0.78	NS	4.02	0.40	NS
Years of Clinical Experience	10.8	0.10	NS	5.10	0.83	NS	1.85	0.93	NS

Note: S-Significant; NS-Not Significant

Table 6 presents the significant relationships between respondents' profile variables (age, sex, educational attainment, and years of clinical experience) and their levels of acceptance of adopting Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP) in terms of attitude, awareness, and willingness.

All computed p-values are greater than 0.05, and all are marked not significant (NS). It indicates that there is no statistically significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their level of acceptance of ANP, thereby accepting the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their level of acceptance of ANP.

In countries with APN, common barriers to acceptance is limited awareness to stakeholders, education sectors and the general public (Moafa et al., 2025). It is imperative that awareness programs be instituted for a successful integration.

Relationship between Capability and Acceptance

Table 7. The significant relationship between the respondents' level of capability and acceptance to adopt advance nursing practice

Dimensions	Attitude			Awareness			Willingness		
	ρ	p	Int	ρ	p	Int	ρ	p	Int
Knowledge	0.36	<.001	S	0.51	<.001	S	0.47	<.001	S
Skills	0.37	<.001	S	0.48	<.001	S	0.47	<.001	S

Experience	0.46	<.001	S	0.51	<.001	S	0.43	<.001	S
APN Competencies	0.46	<.001	S	0.45	<.001	S	0.50	<.001	S

Note: S-Significant; NS-Not Significant

Table 7 examines the relationship between respondents' level of capability (knowledge, skills, experience, and competencies) and their level of acceptance of adopting Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP), measured in terms of attitude, awareness, and willingness.

All relationships show p-values < .001, indicating statistical significance. The correlation coefficients (ρ) range from 0.36 to 0.51, which suggests moderate positive correlations.

For this table, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between Filipino nurses' capability and acceptance of adopting advanced practice nursing.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study's importance stems from the evolution of the Philippine healthcare system, particularly in light of the Universal Health Care (UHC) Act and ongoing legislative support for amending the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002 (RA 9173) to encourage the adoption of advanced nursing practice. The importance of nurses in addressing service delivery gaps, particularly in underprivileged and resource-constrained settings, is increasingly recognized as the nation works to ensure that all Filipinos have equitable, high-quality access to healthcare. The results of this study on Filipino nurses' capability and acceptance of advanced nursing practice demonstrate the profession's readiness to assume expanded roles aligned with international standards. The urgency of this investigation is further highlighted by the current momentum of legislative reforms, which provide empirical data to guide workforce planning, policy development, and the institutionalization of ANP roles within the Philippine healthcare system. In this sense, the study supports national initiatives aimed at bolstering primary care, enhancing health outcomes, and realizing the objectives of universal health care, while also contributing to scholarly discourse.

Based on the study's findings, Filipino nurses generally demonstrate a high level of capability and acceptance to adopt Advanced Nursing Practice (ANP), but various factors influence this.

Educational attainment was found to be a key driver of capability, particularly in knowledge and skills. It suggests that better capability for advanced nursing professions is a result of higher levels of formal education. Age, sex, and years of clinical experience, however, were not shown to have a significant impact on capability, indicating that academic preparation has a greater influence on ANP professional readiness than demographics or duration of service.

Regarding acceptance, the findings showed that respondents' attitude, awareness, and willingness to adopt ANP were not significantly correlated. Acceptance of adopting Advanced Nursing Practice is generally consistent across various professional and demographic groups, indicating a shared openness among Filipino nurses toward the integration of advanced practice roles.

These findings suggest that individual profile characteristics have no bearing on the capability or acceptance of adopting advanced nursing practice. Rather, they are influenced by elements that are shared by all members of the group, such as professional experiences. As a result, programs that support advanced practice nursing may not need to be customized for particular demographic groups; instead, they can be applied widely to all nurses.

In summary, while demographic characteristics do not significantly influence acceptance, capability—particularly enhanced through education and competency development—plays a crucial role in fostering acceptance of Advanced Nursing Practice. It is important to note that improvements across all domains of capability are associated with greater acceptance of ANP among Filipino nurses.

Recommendation

Grounded in the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed to support capability improvement.

Implement Structured Capability-Building Initiatives. Hospitals and health systems should establish continuing professional development (CPD) programs to enhance knowledge, skills, experience, and core competencies aligned with ANP roles. These may include simulation-based training, competency-based workshops, specialty certifications, and mentorship/preceptorship models focusing on advanced clinical skills, leadership, and decision-making. Hospitals with specialty certifications may revisit their training curricula to better align with the ANP model. It supports the study's finding that increased capability leads to higher acceptance.

Foster Inter-Professional Collaboration Early. Engage key stakeholders, particularly physicians and healthcare administrators, in dialogues and planning sessions to define collaborative practice models. Early engagement will promote smoother integration and minimize professional boundary conflicts.

Align Nursing Education and Training with Anticipated ANP Roles. Higher education institutions should begin curriculum enhancement and bridging programs aligned with international ANP standards. Since the study shows that educational attainment significantly affects capability, early academic preparation will ensure a ready workforce once ANP is legalized. Institutions may encourage nurses to pursue post-graduate programs that prepare them for advanced nursing roles.

Conduct continuous research and baseline monitoring. Further research should be encouraged to establish baseline data on capability and acceptance. Conducting the same study in other hospitals may provide a wider view of Filipino nurses' capabilities and acceptance. It will provide empirical support for policy decisions and program adjustments.

Advocate for Legislative and Executive Support. Nursing leaders and professional organizations should continue evidence-based advocacy to support amending the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002, emphasizing the study's findings that Filipino nurses have high levels of capability and strongly accept its adoption regardless of age, sex, educational attainment, and stage of nursing professional development.

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